

Production of a Virtual event on Quality Management and Collaborative International Projects using Scrum as a Project Management Methodology

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Abstract

In a pandemic context caused by covid-19, the education had to adapt to a new global social-political scenario and find different ways to comply with society. In that sense, there is an increasing virtualization that boosts learning-teaching processes in virtual scenarios. The objective of this paper is to publicize the production of a virtual event that presents the results of collaborative international projects, developed by students from the Department of Production Engineering of University of Brasilia, in this time of social distancing. This research is applied, quali-quantitative and descriptive. As data collection technique to measure spectator's satisfaction, it was used a questionnaire, based on a SERVPERF model that measures service quality, that contemplates the evaluation of the criteria such as tangibility, reliability, promptness, security and empathy. The event had 164 people registered and 93 actives, the majority of them students from 4 courses that apply the PBL methodology, and develop projects in an integrated way. The satisfaction evaluation questionnaire was answered by 27 spectators. The average score for the general evaluation of the event was 9.22 on a scale that goes from 1 to 10, a result that displays a high satisfaction index by the spectators with the event. It is feasible to observe that the Scrum methodology was effective for the event project management.

Keywords: virtual event, quality management, collaborative international projects, project-based learning

1 Introduction

With the arrival of the first cases of SARS-CoV-2 pandemic to Brazil and in the middle of an international public calamity, the Brazilian government decreed a set of temporary actions aiming to contain the spread of the Covid-19 disease. One of them was the suspension of face-to-face academic activities in higher education institutions (Brazil, 2020). According to Ferreira (2020), this suspension led to a transformation in the regular functioning of higher education institutions with great impact on the entire academic community, especially on students.

As a consequence of the pandemic, in-person academic events were also impacted. Thus, remote teaching has become a reality, highlighting, therefore, the relevance of online academic events in the learning process. Events of this nature are an essential source in the search for new knowledge, by bringing together and presenting renowned professionals in the area of interest (Jesus et al., 2020).

Even with the impossibility of physical presence, some student-centered, active learning methodologies can be applied in the construction of education during this period. A widely used methodology is Project-Based Learning (PBL), which encourages the integration of new knowledge through the challenge of developing projects (Dewi; Kristanto, 2019).

For this reason, through this scenario of uncertainty and project development in the PBL context, stands out the use of the agile methodology, with the SCRUM framework. Traditional methods present robust planning, whereas agile methodologies have dynamic planning, which allows a quick and effective response to changes in the expectations of its stakeholders, so this way of managing projects reduces possible losses and increases gains. The SCRUM methodology was considered appropriate for this object of study, that are projects developed in disciplines of three and a half months duration (Scrumstudy, 2017).

This work aims to present the SCRUM management methodology to produce a virtual event and its results, based on the presentation of projects developed by students of the Production Engineering undergraduate at the University of Brasilia (UnB), within disciplines that apply to the PBL methodology. The online event permits the dissemination of results from projects developed in partnership with international institutions and concepts of Quality Management, brought by lectures given by professionals from nationally renowned companies.

This paper is structured in 5 sections: section 2 presents the literature review; section 3 shows the methodology; section 4 highlights the results and discussions and finally, section 5 presents the conclusions.

2 Bibliographic Review

This section offers the theoretical background needed to conduct the research.

2.1 Production of scientific events

The achievement of an academic event is the opportunity to deliver social value, generate knowledge and publicize brands, promoting true networking (Lacerda, 2019). According to Kotler (2000), one way to generate referrals for the company is "by engaging in events or activities that attract public attention." This source also points out that events are activities that attract attention and are an occasion for the development of items targeted to different audiences.

For Saito, Hiramoto, and Saito (2009), scientific knowledge made public, in forums, meetings or journals, promotes a discussion that enriches studies and it favors the advancement of science. To promote an event, a management methodology must be employed, because the event was built in the perspective of a project. The management methodology used in this study is discussed in section 2.2.

2.2 SCRUM methodology for project management

In a research conducted by Teixeira, Maccari and Kniess (2012), it was concluded that the main problems encountered in event execution are due to the absence of a responsible person or a management methodology. That's why it's essential to select the right tools to manage the event production project for this study: the SCRUM management methodology, "an extremely agile and flexible methodology" (Bissi, 2007).

SCRUM is based on adaptation and iteration, ensuring transparency in communication and continuous improvement (Scrumstudy, 2017). The method provides artifacts such as "product backlog" and "sprints", promoting the minimization of risks and offering users a quick and continuous evaluation (Silva and Silva, 2009).

To monitor the steps of the methodology applied in this research, the tools employed were an adaptation of Kanban, "one of the simplest and most popular tools in the agile world" (Dantas; De Aquino Junior, 2016) and the agile rites. The tools were accessed by the mentoring teachers and the work team simultaneously. The application of this model resulted in a virtual event, whose theme is explained in section 2.3.

2.3 Virtual events

Inserted in a pandemic context due to Covid-19, the event was held through virtual tools. Belloni (2002) explains that technologies are already part of all fields of social life, and that applies to education as well. It's fundamental to understand that social changes also modify the individual's perception and learning process, demanding radical transformations in the educational systems (Belloni, 2002). This statement is still relevant since, in recent studies, Mayes (2018) declares that the study of relations in the learning process can offer a deeper understanding of the society.

For De Sousa Oliveira Eleilde et al. (2020), this perception corroborates the idea that non-presence education is a trend that emerged suddenly during the Covid-19 quarantine period and tends to become even more common, so educational institutions are increasing their offers to meet this new demand. Consequently, there has been a transformation in the functioning of higher education institutions (Ferreira, 2020). Now with virtual communications the public can be better anticipated since it's understood that the situation should no longer

be conceived as it was before. In this critical period, we must consider the virtual resources in a planned way (De Sousa Oliveira Eleilde et al., 2020).

The requirements for keeping students motivated through extracurricular activities is still demanded, along with the need for health's preservation: that's why an online event is an excellent alternative (Jesus et. al, 2020). It's also important not to forget the need to keep the audience's attention, considering the distraction scenario that a distance relationship can promote (Event Skift Brand, 2020). The event was produced in a virtual way, and was evaluated through the application of a questionnaire, which is explained in section 2.4.

2.4 Measuring results

To measure the public's satisfaction with the event held, a feedback of research should be conducted. With the application of a questionnaire in the academic event, it is possible to evaluate the audience's satisfaction and the quality of the lectures (De Freitas Faria et al., 2019). Hence, with a lot of planning, execution activities and verification, it's possible to refine processes and develop improvements to act on future experiences. This is the well-known PDCA cycle (plan, do, check, action) (Kume, 1993).

The results can be measured through questionnaires oriented to the satisfaction of the user of a service, since an academic event is a service too. One of the possible questionnaires in this sense is the one proposed by the SERVQUAL model, suggested by Manuela Krystyna Ingaldi (2017). The model proposes that the quality evaluated is given by means of "gaps". The gap is the difference between customer expectation and the performance of the service provided. (Salomi; Miguel; Abackerli, 2005). On the other hand, SERVPERF is another evaluation model that suggests that the quality is based only on the perception of the service, that is, the performance of the service provided is equal to the quality evaluation (Cronin and Taylor, 1992). The satisfaction measurement of the event was grounded on the SERVPERF model and the Net Promoter Score (NPS) indicator, an effective method for generating indicators and analyzing improvements (Oliveira, Vieira, Kovaleski, 2016).

The scope of the results presented at the event covers proposals originated from project disciplines that adopt the Project-Based Learning (PBL) methodology, in order to present solutions to real problems. This topic is detailed in section 2.5.

2.5 Project- Based Learning (PBL)

The premise of the event was the unveiling of results from interdisciplinary projects, developed within a process in which students are the main agent of learning. The learners are instigated to solve the problems presented (Delisle; Oliveira, 2000). For Barrows (1986), within the context of active learning such as Project-Based Learning (PBL), teachers play the role of facilitators of the process, but it's the student who must discover tools and methods capable of generating solutions to the problem at hand.

Therefore, new skills are developed and the learners become committed to the search for knowledge through curiosity and questioning that may arise (Barell, 2007).

However, for X. Du et al. (2009), in order to analyse the advantages and disadvantages of PBL, the most advantageous situation would be to have small-scale studies that provide details and large-scale studies that aim at representativeness. It would also be beneficial to have interinstitutional studies, both nationally and internationally.

Section 3 displays the complete methodology of the research design and project execution, seeking to clarify how the results were obtained.

3 Methodology

The methodology presents the research method and its structure.

3.1 Research Method

The research related to this article is characterized as, regarding its nature, an applied research, since it deals with a phenomenon that, in fact, generated knowledge of practical application (Silveira; Córdova, 2009). As for the objectives, the research is descriptive, because of the request of a semi-structured questionnaire to those enrolled in the event to measure the quality of the service provided at the end of the project. According to Fonseca (2002) this type of study is a survey research.

The research approach employed to present the results is qualitative and quantitative, since the results were subjected to a qualitative analysis of learning, considering that it uses an observation perspective, and concludes the reasoning with subsidy from the listed quantitative results of the questionnaire. The Qualitative analysis prioritizes the observation of the phenomenon (Silveira; Córdova, 2009), being the predominant objective of this study.

The main source for studying the subject were articles, other types of academic papers, books and manuals. A questionnaire was applied as a technique to collect data on the satisfaction of the event's audience. Out of 93 viewers who accessed the virtual event, 27 answered the questionnaire, representing a sample of 29% of the total viewers. The quality criteria evaluated were tangibility, reliability, promptness, security, and empathy. The research was structured in stages presented in the following section.

3.2 Structure of the research

It was structured in four consecutive stages, plus a management stage, simultaneous to the others, whose specifications can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Structure of the research, done by the authors.

The first stage consisted of a literature review, whose search platform was the Web Of Science and Google Scholar, utilizing the keywords: "academic events", "technology", "marketing", "quality management", "questionnaire", "servqual", "servperf", "scrum", "research classification", "virtual events" and "virtual education". This examination was fundamental to define the objectives and describe the first steps toward them.

In the second stage, it was necessary to search for pre-existing and already validated questionnaires to develop the one that would be used to evaluate the event. With minor adaptations, the questionnaire was developed and based on the SERVPERF model. This was the best choice, since the participants could only be interviewed regarding the perception of the service, without a prior analysis of their expectations.

The third stage consists in hosting the event itself. As a premise, it was defined that the event would be virtual due to the Covid-19 pandemic and that registrations would be free. Negotiation techniques were used through compensation, where both parties win, so that partnerships and lectures could be established. To the event

partners, the dissemination of their brands through the Instagram platform was a means of compensation, and to the lecturers, a certificate of participation was negotiated.

The literature was also an excellent support for the application of the event's development project management methodology. This, in turn, was pre-defined as an agile methodology, using the SCRUM framework. The agile methodology allowed the deliveries to be executed in small activity cycles (sprints) within a large project for feedback from the interested parties. The results of this research follow in section 4.

4 Results and Discussions

This section has the results of the event development project in terms of: (i) event planning, (ii) the event and (iii) post-event.

4.1 Event planning

To prepare the event planning, the team listed and divided the main tasks to be executed in columns of an online visual management chart: "backlog", "to do", "doing", "for evaluation" and "completed". In this way, a chart was made available to all members of the event organization team, consequently facilitating the identification of the requirements of the final product, as well as the activities that were being executed by the team.

This team held biweekly meetings with the stakeholders, over a period of three months, with the objective of aligning expectations and adjusting requirements. These meetings showed the need to define the theme, name, promotion and presentation platforms, number of speakers, and other factors of the event, such as the name "Quality Management virtual event". It was publicized by the social network Instagram and presented by Sympla Streaming.

Still in the planning stage, two lectures and a workshop were defined, as well as the need to bring to public notice the projects executed in the active learning disciplines of the Production Engineering course at UnB. The best ones were selected by the organizers of the event and professors, through the following pre-established criteria: social contribution of the problem, definition of the objectives, strategy adopted, cohesion in the development of the research, deadline performance and methodology employed. It is worth mentioning that all 8 projects designated for presentation, including the one that made it possible, were developed with the support of the Project-Based Learning (PBL) methodology. The activities involved in the event are displayed in section 4.2.

4.2 The event

The academic event was developed according to a pre-established schedule and occurred on two consecutive days, November 25 and 26, 2020, lasting three (3) hours each. The organization team took charge of the event, introducing the workshop, the lectures, and the projects. The choice to hold the event in two days was the result of a previous study that found the need to divide a large event into sub-events, so that the public's attention would be improved (Event Skift Brand, 2020).

The event had 164 people registered and 93 actives, counting with the presence of 52 participants simultaneously during the online presentations. This process helped in the preparation of questions to the lecturers, in order to contribute to the development of the activity. The lectures were given by representatives of three companies that are exponents in each of their fields. Regarding the 8 projects, they were presented by students from 5 different courses of the Production Systems Projects (PSPs) from the Production Engineering undergraduate at UnB. These disciplines belong to the areas of Research Methodology for Production Engineering; Personal Finances, Statistical Probability; Information System applied to Production Engineering with focus on System Requirements Surveying; Quality Management; and Project Integration Management.

It is noteworthy that the projects presented were interdisciplinary, so that the 8 teams from the 5 different disciplines worked in an integrated way to achieve the exposed results. Besides, some of the proposed themes involved international partnerships with Aalborg University, Denmark, for the Mobile Education project and

Esprit University, Tunisia, for the PUMA project (Unified Platform of Active Methodologies, acronyms in Portuguese).

The projects presented were evaluated in real time by the event's audience and the teachers of the disciplines related to the projects, who were part of an evaluation panel. This made possible that the best ones could be awarded as a form of incentive to the students. The teams' scores were given by the following weighted average:

$$M = NPG + 2*NPROF (1)$$

where M is the team's final average, NPG represents the average of the scores of the event's audiences and NPROF represents the average of the teachers' scores. The teachers' grades had a greater weight in the team's final average, since a more technical content was sought in the awarding of the projects presented.

The event was guided by concepts of Quality Management; therefore, a questionnaire was applied as a means to understand if the service provided met the public's expectations.

4.3 Post-event

As previously explained in the methodology, the evaluation counted on an adaptation of the SERVPERF model, because the questionnaire pre-established by this model aims at a physical service, which is tangible. Accordingly, the quality criteria of tangibility, reliability, promptness, security and empathy (Salomi; Miguel; Abackerli, 2005), were employed to develop the questionnaire for the service of production of a virtual event, as presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Criteria adapted from the SERVPERF model for producing a virtual event.

Criteria	Related Questions
Tangibility	The workshop, lectures and projects presented were fruitful, presented visually pleasing slides that were easy to understand?
Reliability	Did the event faithfully meet its opening and closing times?
Promptness	Did the event ceremonial adequately inform about schedules, attend promptly to the public, and were they organized?
Security	Was the organizers' contact with the public easy and safe, and did they offer interesting raffles and clear and appropriate promotion?
Empathy	Was the event dynamic, did it meet the audience's expectations, and was it able to keep their attention?

The questionnaire was previously validated with a group of 10 people to be applied later. The public's understanding of the questions was tested with male and female representatives. The questionnaire was answered by 27 people, 37.03% female and 62.96% male. This means an adherence of 29% of the total audience to the questionnaire. However, of the total of 93 people, only 52 were able to fully evaluate the event, as they participated in the event in its entirety. In this case, the sample represents approximately 52% of 52 people. The results are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Quality Criteria evaluated by the SERVPERF model, chart elaborated by the authors.

Through the scores attributed to the evaluated criteria, it is understood, therefore, that interactivity and dissemination (security criterion) and the use of the lectures, workshops and projects (tangibility criterion) were the best evaluated, with averages of 9.48 and 9.33, respectively. Punctuality (reliability criterion) and ceremonial performance (promptness criterion) were tied in the evaluation, with an average of 9.14. The ability to entertain, educate, and keep the audience's attention (empathy criterion) resulted in the lowest average, 9.00. The overall average for the criteria was 9.22.

The lowest scores were attributed to the reliability, promptness, and empathy criteria. The lowest individual score given in the whole evaluation was 6.00 for reliability, more specifically punctuality. That was because some factors are beyond the organizers' total control and the punctuality of the lecturers was one of them.

All in all, on a scale of 1 to 10, the criteria were well evaluated as there was no individual average lower than 9.00. Figure 1 shows the overall evaluation of the event.

Figure 3. Overall evaluation of the virtual event, provided by the authors.

The scores were attributed as follows: 15 people gave a score of 10.0 as a general evaluation; 9 participants gave a score of 9.0 and 3 people associated the event with an 8.0 score. In the overall evaluation, the average grade given was 9.44 (on a scale of 1 to 10). Using the understanding given by the Net Promoter Score (NPS) indicator, by a simple calculation, % promoters (scores 9 and 10) - % neutrals (scores 7 and 8) - detractors (scores 1 until 6) = NPS. The evaluators who gave a score of 1.0 to 6.0 were considered detractors, in other words, they were not satisfied. Those who gave a score between 7.0 and 8.0 were considered neutral. On the other hand, the evaluators who gave a score between 9.00 and 10.00 were considered promoters, that is, they were satisfied.

It's understood that, according to the survey results, among the respondents, 24 were promoters and only 3 neutral ones (Oliveira, Vieira, Kovaleski, 2016).

In order to complement the results obtained and show the opinion of the viewers and the presenters, anonymous feedback testimonies were included, transcribed below, which reiterate the result.

"Very good event! We learned a lot from the lectures, in addition to having an overview of what was done in the course. Very positive!"

"Wonderful and very organized event. The organizers were very competent."

"Excellent event! Of course, dynamic and very knowledgeable."

In addition, the organizers approached their experiences as something that a new perspective of learning in the team, through an active methodology and, where they became protagonists of the teaching process in Production Engineering and its projects in a pandemic context. An ease was added in the general understanding of teaching that they did not have before.

5 Conclusion

Despite the huge impact in education and teaching due to the Covid-19 pandemic, it was possible to adapt to the new reality by using a virtual event as an option for learning strategy. In this article we present our methodology for the project management and the results obtained by planning, executing and evaluating of the event, therefore, fulfilling our research objective.

The activities of the event were executed by a team of students from the discipline of Projects related to the Quality Management (PSP5), in a way that the active learning methodology was a fundamental agent in the development of the event during this period of pandemic. In addition, the PBL methodology allowed a greater protagonism of the students in the organization of the event.

As a form of project management, the SCRUM framework succeeds to meet the expectations of a service project. The possible disappointments regarding the results and evaluations were avoided by periodically aligning the needs of all stakeholders, until the final stages of the project. The event could be considered satisfactory, based on the results obtained in the post-event, a general average of 9.44, on a scale of 0 to 10 was obtained, becoming a very positive evaluation by the participants.

In relation to the objectives, were achieved by presenting the results in interdisciplinary international projects from 3 different countries. In addition, the lectures and the workshop contributed to the teaching-learning of Quality Management concepts, in a way that didn't cause any health risk to any stakeholder.

As a limitation of the research, we can underline the little coverage of the event, since it was 100% online and no physical means of divulgation was used due to the pandemic conditions. Furthermore, the themes of the lectures and the workshop were restricted to the Quality Management areas.

Finally, as future work, it's recommended to expand the themes of the lectures and workshops, aiming to cover other areas besides Quality Management, that is, an event with a wider range of themes and audiences. Also, in a non-pandemic scenario, we suggest a greater divulgation of the event, relying on physical means, as well as the realization of a hybrid event, with remote and in-person possibilities.

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